

On Bipolar Fuzzy Soft Clusters

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce the concept of a bipolar fuzzy soft cluster and derive its key results. We explore the structural properties of this concept and investigate its connections with ultra bipolar fuzzy soft filters and bipolar fuzzy soft proximity spaces. Through these analyses, we highlight the importance of BFS in advancing the exploration of proximity-based systems within the bipolar fuzzy soft framework.

1. Introduction

Classical methods are inadequate in addressing various uncertainties in solving complex problems in fields such as economics, engineering, and the environment. To overcome these uncertainties, numerous theories have been proposed. The most well-known theories are fuzzy set theory, introduced by Zadeh [31] in 1965, and rough set theory, introduced by Pawlak [20] in 1982. While these theories are useful tools for dealing with uncertainties, as pointed out by Molodtsov [17], they face certain difficulties and limitations due to the insufficiency of parameterization tools. To address these issues, Molodtsov [17] introduced the concept of soft sets, which handle uncertainties and imprecisions in a parametric manner. Since its inception, the soft set theory has been widely utilized by researchers as a powerful tool to define uncertainties. For example, Maji [15] et al. explored concepts such as subset, union, intersection, and complement in the context of soft sets. Additionally, Maji [16] et al. introduced a more general concept, the fuzzy soft set, which combines the ideas of fuzzy sets and soft sets. Ali [2] et al. proposed new algebraic operations on soft sets and investigated their properties, while Shabir and Naz [26] studied soft topological spaces. Kharal and Ahmad [10] introduced mappings on classes of fuzzy soft sets and examined the properties of fuzzy soft images. Demir et al. [6] further investigated the convergence of fuzzy soft filters in fuzzy soft topological spaces. However, fuzzy sets cannot adequately represent the degree to which an element satisfies a counter-property. To address this, Lee [14] proposed the

concept of bipolar-valued fuzzy sets, where the membership degree ranges from $[-1, 1]$, allowing for the coexistence of negativity and positivity. In bipolar fuzzy sets, a membership value of 0 indicates that an element is irrelevant to the property, a value in the range $(0, 1]$ means the element somewhat satisfies the property, and a value in the range $[-1, 0)$ means the element somewhat satisfies the counter-property. Building on this, Abdullah [1] et al. and Naz and Shabir [18] independently developed the concept of bipolar fuzzy soft sets (BFS-sets), combining bipolar fuzzy sets and soft sets. Riaz and Tehrim [23] introduced bipolar fuzzy soft topology (BFS-topology) and discussed several aspects of BFS-topology. They also demonstrated the application of BFS-sets to medical diagnosis problems. In recent years, there has been significant literature on BFS-sets and their applications, highlighting both their theoretical importance and practical relevance.

In 1951, Efremovic [9] introduced the concept of proximity structures, which provided a foundational framework for addressing various topological challenges, such as compactification, extension problems, and the axiomatization of geometric concepts. This breakthrough laid the groundwork for the study of proximity spaces, further advanced by Naimpally and Warrack [18], whose work spurred subsequent developments in this area. For instance, Katsaras [12], utilizing fuzzy sets, formulated an approach to proximity structures, while Artico and Moresco [3] introduced a distinct notion of fuzzy proximity. In addition, Ramadan et al. [21] expanded this area by presenting fuzzifying proximity structures. Extending these ideas, several researchers have explored proximity structures within the contexts of soft sets and fuzzy soft sets. Kandil et al. [10]

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defined soft proximity spaces and examined their fundamental properties. Singh and Singh [27] introduced the notions of soft proximity bases and subbases. Later, Cetkin et al. [4] proposed soft fuzzy proximity spaces based on Katsaras [12] axioms, while Demir and Özbakır [8] further developed the concept by studying fuzzy soft proximity spaces and showing how they can lead to the derivation of fuzzy soft topologies.

Yu. M. Smirnov [28] was the first to address the compactification of proximity spaces. Leader [13] proposed the concept of a cluster, which is the analogue of an ultrafilter in a proximity space and offers a different method for solving various proximity problems. In particular, Leader [13] determined that the family of all clusters in a proximity space X is its compactification.

In this paper, we present the concept of a bipolar fuzzy soft cluster and establish its fundamental results. We examine the structural characteristics of this notion and analyze its relationships with ultra bipolar fuzzy soft filters and bipolar fuzzy soft proximity spaces. Our investigation emphasize the significance of bipolar fuzzy soft clusters in advancing the comprehension of proximity-based systems within the bipolar fuzzy soft framework.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we review some basic notions of BFS-sets that we will use in the subsequent sections. Throughout this paper, U be a universe of alternatives (objects), and E be a set of specified parameters (criteria or attributes) unless otherwise explicit.

Definition 2.1. [14] Consider a universal set U . A set having form

$$\eta = \left\{ \left(u, \delta_{\eta}^{+}(u), \delta_{\eta}^{-}(u) \right) : u \in U \right\}$$

denotes a bipolar fuzzy set on U , where $\delta_{\eta}^{+}(u)$ denotes the positive memberships ranges over $[0,1]$ and $\delta_{\eta}^{-}(u)$ denotes the negative memberships ranges over $[-1,0]$.

Definition 2.2. [14] Let η_1 and η_2 be two bipolar fuzzy sets on U . Then, their intersection and union are defined as follows:

- (i) $\eta_1 \wedge \eta_2 = \left\{ \left(u, \min\{\delta_{\eta_1}^{+}(u), \delta_{\eta_2}^{+}(u)\}, \max\{\delta_{\eta_1}^{-}(u), \delta_{\eta_2}^{-}(u)\} \right) : u \in U \right\}$
- (ii) $\eta_1 \vee \eta_2 = \left\{ \left(u, \max\{\delta_{\eta_1}^{+}(u), \delta_{\eta_2}^{+}(u)\}, \min\{\delta_{\eta_1}^{-}(u), \delta_{\eta_2}^{-}(u)\} \right) : u \in U \right\}$.

Definition 2.3. [1,19] Consider a universal set U and a set of parameters E . Let $A \subseteq E$ and define a mapping $\Omega : E \rightarrow BF^U$, where BF^U represents the family of all bipolar fuzzy

subsets of U . Then, Ω_A is called a BFS-set on U , where

$$\Omega_A = \{ \langle e, \Omega(e) \rangle : e \in E \}$$

such that $\delta_{\Omega(e)}^{+}(u) = \delta_{\Omega(e)}^{-}(u) = 0$ for all $e \notin A$ and all $u \in U$. Note that the set of all bipolar fuzzy soft sets on U with the attributes from E is denoted by $(BF^U)^E$.

Definition 2.4. [32] (i) A BFS-set $\Omega_E \in (BF^U)^E$ is called an absolute BFS-set, denoted by U_E , if $\delta_{\Omega(e)}^{+}(u) = 1$ and $\delta_{\Omega(e)}^{-}(u) = -1$ for all $u \in U$ and all $e \in E$.

(ii) A BFS-set $\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E$ is called a null BFS-set, denoted by \emptyset_A , if $\delta_{\Omega(e)}^{+}(u) = \delta_{\Omega(e)}^{-}(u) = 0$ for all $u \in U$ and all $e \in A$.

Definition 2.5. [1,19] Let $\Omega_{A_1}^1, \Omega_{A_2}^2 \in (BF^U)^E$. Then,

(i) The union of $\Omega_{A_1}^1$ and $\Omega_{A_2}^2$ is a bipolar fuzzy soft set $\Omega_{A_3}^3$ over U such that for all $e \in E$, $\Omega^3(e) = \Omega^1(e) \vee \Omega^2(e)$ and denoted by $\Omega_{A_3}^3 = \Omega_{A_1}^1 \tilde{\cup} \Omega_{A_2}^2$.

(ii) The intersection of $\Omega_{A_1}^1$ and $\Omega_{A_2}^2$ is a bipolar fuzzy soft set $\Omega_{A_3}^3$ over U such that for all $e \in E$, $\Omega^3(e) = \Omega^1(e) \wedge \Omega^2(e)$ and denoted by $\Omega_{A_3}^3 = \Omega_{A_1}^1 \tilde{\cap} \Omega_{A_2}^2$.

Definition 2.6. [1,19] The complement of a BFS-set $\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E$ is shown by $(\Omega_A)^c = \Omega_{A_1}^c$ where $\Omega^c : E \rightarrow BF^U$ is a mapping defined by $\delta_{\Omega^c(e)}^{+}(u) = 1 - \delta_{\Omega(e)}^{+}(u)$ and $\delta_{\Omega^c(e)}^{-}(u) = -1 - \delta_{\Omega(e)}^{-}(u)$ for all $e \in E$ and $u \in U$.

Theorem 2.7. [19] Let $\Omega_{A_1}^1, \Omega_{A_2}^2$ be two BFS-sets over U .

- (i) $((\Omega_{A_1}^1)^c)^c = \Omega_{A_1}^1$.
- (ii) If $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \tilde{\subseteq} \Omega_{A_2}^2$, then $(\Omega_{A_2}^2)^c \tilde{\subseteq} (\Omega_{A_1}^1)^c$.
- (iii) $(\Omega_{A_1}^1 \tilde{\cap} \Omega_{A_2}^2)^c = (\Omega_{A_1}^1)^c \tilde{\cup} (\Omega_{A_2}^2)^c$.
- (iv) $(\Omega_{A_1}^1 \tilde{\cup} \Omega_{A_2}^2)^c = (\Omega_{A_1}^1)^c \tilde{\cap} (\Omega_{A_2}^2)^c$.

Definition 2.8. [32] Let $\Omega_{A_1}^1, \Omega_{A_2}^2 \in (BF^U)^E$. Then, $\Omega_{A_1}^1$ is a BFS-subset of $\Omega_{A_2}^2$ if $\delta_{\Omega^1(e)}^{+}(u) \leq \delta_{\Omega^2(e)}^{+}(u)$ and $\delta_{\Omega^1(e)}^{-}(u) \geq \delta_{\Omega^2(e)}^{-}(u)$, which is shown by $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \tilde{\subseteq} \Omega_{A_2}^2$.

Definition 2.9. [7] Let $\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E$ with $A = \{e\}$. If there is a $u \in U$ such that $\delta_{\Omega(e)}^{+}(u) \neq 0$ or $\delta_{\Omega(e)}^{-}(u) \neq 0$ and $\delta_{\Omega(e)}^{+}(u') = \delta_{\Omega(e)}^{-}(u') = 0$ for all $u' \in U \setminus \{u\}$, then Ω_A is called a BFS-point in U . It is denoted by $e_u^{(p,n)}$.

Definition 2.10. [7] The BFS-point $e_u^{(p,n)}$ is said to belongs to a BFS-set Ω_A , denoted by $e_u^{(p,n)} \tilde{\in} \Omega_A$, if $p \leq \delta_{\Omega(e)}^{+}(u)$ and $n \geq \delta_{\Omega(e)}^{-}(u)$.

Definition 2.11. [22] Let $(BF^U)^E$ and $(BF^V)^D$ be two the families of all bipolar fuzzy soft sets on U and V with parameters from E and D, respectively. Assume that $u: U \rightarrow V$ and $g: E \rightarrow D$ be two mappings. Then, the mapping $f = (u, g): (BF^U)^E \rightarrow (BF^V)^D$ is called a BFS-mapping from U to V.

Theorem 2.12. [22] Let $f = (u, g): (BF^U)^E \rightarrow (BF^V)^D$ be a BFS-mapping. Then, for $\Omega_{A_1}^1, \Omega_{A_2}^2 \in (BF^U)^E$ and $\Gamma_{B_1}^1, \Gamma_{B_2}^2 \in (BF^V)^D$, the following properties are satisfied.

- (i) $f(\Omega_{A_1}^1 \cup \Omega_{A_2}^2) = f(\Omega_{A_1}^1) \cup f(\Omega_{A_2}^2)$.
- (ii) $f^{-1}(\Gamma_{B_1}^1 \cup \Gamma_{B_2}^2) = f^{-1}(\Gamma_{B_1}^1) \cup f^{-1}(\Gamma_{B_2}^2)$.
- (iii) $f(\Omega_{A_1}^1 \cap \Omega_{A_2}^2) \subseteq f(\Omega_{A_1}^1) \cap f(\Omega_{A_2}^2)$.
- (iv) $f^{-1}(\Gamma_{B_1}^1 \cap \Gamma_{B_2}^2) = f^{-1}(\Gamma_{B_1}^1) \cap f^{-1}(\Gamma_{B_2}^2)$.
- (v) $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \subseteq f^{-1}(f(\Omega_{A_1}^1)), f(f^{-1}(\Gamma_{B_1}^1)) \subseteq \Gamma_{B_1}^1$.

Definition 2.13. [23] A family τ of BFS-sets over U is said to be a BFS-topology on U if it satisfies the following properties:

- (bfst₁) U_E and \emptyset_A are members of τ .
- (bfst₂) If $\Omega_{A_i}^i \in \tau$ for all $i \in \Lambda$, an index set, then $\bigcup \Omega_{A_i}^i \in \tau$.
- (bfst₃) If $\Omega_{A_1}^1, \Omega_{A_2}^2 \in \tau$, then $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \cap \Omega_{A_2}^2 \in \tau$.

Definition 2.14. [23] Let (U, τ, E) be a BFS-topological space and $\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E$. The BFS-interior of Ω_A is the union of all BFS-open sets contained in Ω_A , denoted by $(\Omega_A)^\circ$. From (bfst₂) it is clear that $(\Omega_A)^\circ$ is a BFS-open set. This set is largest BFS-open set contained in Ω_A .

Definition 2.15. [23] Let (U, τ, E) be a BFS-topological space and $\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E$. The closure of Ω_A is the intersection of all BFS-closed sets containing Ω_A ; this set is denoted $\overline{\Omega_A}$. It is easily seen that $\overline{\Omega_A}$ is the smallest closed set containing Ω_A .

Definition 2.16. [6] Let $(U, \tau_1, E), (V, \tau_2, D)$ be two BFS-topological spaces and $f = (u, g): (U, \tau_1, E) \rightarrow (V, \tau_2, D)$ be a BFS-mapping. The BFS-mapping f is said to be BFS-continuous if $f^{-1}(\Gamma_B) \in \tau_1$ for any $\Gamma_B \in \tau_2$.

Definition 2.17. [24] Consider a set U and a subset Z of U. Then, a mapping $Y^Z: E \rightarrow (BF^U)^E$ is a BFS-set on U_E defined as in the following way: For all $e \in E$,

$$Y^Z(e) = \{(u, \delta_{Y^Z(e)}^+(u), \delta_{Y^Z(e)}^-(u)): u \in U\}$$

where

$$\delta_{Y^Z(e)}^+(u) = \begin{cases} 1, & u \in Z, \\ 0, & u \notin Z, \end{cases}$$

$$\delta_{Y^Z(e)}^-(u) = \begin{cases} -1, & u \in Z, \\ 0, & u \notin Z. \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.18. [6] A BFS-filter F on U is a nonempty collection of subsets of $(BF^U)^E$ if it satisfies the following conditions:

- (BFSF1) $\emptyset_A \notin F$,
- (BFSF2) If $\Omega_{A_1}^1, \Omega_{A_2}^2 \in F$, then $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \cap \Omega_{A_2}^2 \in F$,
- (BFSF3) If $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \in F$ and $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \subseteq \Omega_{A_2}^2$ then $\Omega_{A_2}^2 \in F$.

Definition 2.18. [6] Let B be a subcollection of a BFS-filter F such that for every $\Omega_A \in F$, there is an $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \in B$ with $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \subseteq \Omega_A$. We call such an B a BFS-base of F.

Theorem 2.19. [6] Let $f = (u, g): (BF^U)^E \rightarrow (BF^V)^D$ be a BFS-mapping and let F be a BFS-filter on U. Then, $B^* = \{f(\Omega_A): \Omega_A \in F\}$ is a BFS-base for a BFS-filter f(F) on V.

Proof. (B₁) is obvious.

(B₂) Suppose that $f(\Omega_{A_1}^1), f(\Omega_{A_2}^2) \in B^*$. Then, we have to show that $f(\Omega_{A_3}^3) \in B^*$ such that $f(\Omega_{A_3}^3) \subseteq f(\Omega_{A_1}^1) \cap f(\Omega_{A_2}^2)$. Since $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \cap \Omega_{A_2}^2 \in F$, we obtain $f(\Omega_{A_1}^1 \cap \Omega_{A_2}^2) \in B^*$. Then, by Theorem 2.13, this implies $f(\Omega_{A_1}^1 \cap \Omega_{A_2}^2) \subseteq f(\Omega_{A_3}^3) \cap f(\Omega_{A_2}^2)$. Thus, the proof ends.

Definition 2.20. [6] If F_1, F_2 are two BFS-filters on U, we say that F_2 is finer than F_1 (or F_1 is coarser than F_2) if and only if $F_2 \supseteq F_1$.

Definition 2.21. [6] If a BFS-filter F on U has the property that there is no BFS-filter on U which is finer than F, then F is called an ultra BFS-filter on U.

Theorem 2.22. [6] Let F be a BFS-filter on U. Then, there exists an ultra BFS-filter F^* on U such that $F \subseteq F^*$.

Proof. Let F be a collection that contains all the BFS-filters finer than F on U such that it is partially ordered by the relation " \supseteq " given in Definition 2.22. Consider an chain $\{F_i: i \in J\} \subseteq F$. Then $\bigcup_{i \in J} F_i$ is a BFS-filter on U and also it is an upper bound of $\{F_i: i \in J\}$. Using Zorn's Lemma, we see that F has a maximal element F^* . Hence, F^* is a ultra BFS-filter containing F.

Theorem 2.23. [6] Let F be a BFS-filter on U. Then,

- (i) F is an ultra BFS-filter on U if and only if each $\Gamma_B \in$

$(BF^U)^E$ satisfying $\Gamma_B \tilde{\cap} \Omega_A \neq \emptyset_A$ for every $\Omega_A \in F$ is contained in F .

(ii) If F is an ultra BFS-filter on U and $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \tilde{\cup} \Omega_{A_2}^2 \in F$, then we have $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \in F$ or $\Omega_{A_2}^2 \in F$.

(iii) If F is an ultra BFS-filter on U , then for all $\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E$, we get $\Omega_A \in F$ or $(\Omega_A)^c \in F$.

Proof (i) Let F be an ultra BFS-filter on U . Consider that $\Gamma_B \in (BF^U)^E$ satisfying $\Omega_A \tilde{\cap} \Gamma_B \neq \emptyset_A$ for all $\Omega_A \in F$. Take $M = F \cup \{\Gamma_B\}$. Because M has the finite intersection property, from Lemma there is a BFS-filter L on U with $M \subseteq L$. So, from Definition 2.23, it is easily seen that $F = L$. Thus, we obtain $\Gamma_B \in F$.

Conversely, assume that F includes all $\Gamma_B \in (BF^U)^E$ such that $\Omega_A \tilde{\cap} \Gamma_B \neq \emptyset_A$ for all $\Omega_A \in F$. Let us create a BFS-filter M satisfying $F \subseteq M$. Therefore, we have $\Lambda_C \in (BF^U)^E$ such that $\Lambda_C \in M$ and $\Lambda_C \notin F$. Now, choose any $\Omega_A \in F$. Therefore, by the property of BFS-filter, we have $\Omega_A \tilde{\cap} \Lambda_C \neq \emptyset_A$. Thus, from hypothesis, it follows that $\Lambda_C \in F$, which leads to a contradiction.

(ii) Let $\Omega_{A_1}^1, \Omega_{A_2}^2 \notin F$ and assume that $\Omega_A = \Omega_{A_1}^1 \tilde{\cup} \Omega_{A_2}^2 \in F$. From (i) there are $\Gamma_{B_1}^1, \Gamma_{B_2}^2 \in F$ such that $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \tilde{\cap} \Gamma_{B_1}^1 = \Omega_{A_2}^2 \tilde{\cap} \Gamma_{B_2}^2 = \emptyset_A$. If $\Gamma_B = \Gamma_{B_1}^1 \tilde{\cap} \Gamma_{B_2}^2$, then we possess $\Gamma_B \in F$ and $\Gamma_B \tilde{\cap} \Omega_A = \emptyset_A$. It can be understood from these expressions that $\Omega_A \notin F$, a contradiction.

(iii) Let F be an ultra BFS-filter on U . Suppose that $\Omega_A, (\Omega_A)^c \notin F$. From (ii) we know that $\Omega_A \tilde{\cup} (\Omega_A)^c = \Omega_{A_1}^1 \notin F$. Then, by (i), there exists an $\Omega_{A_2}^2 \in F$ satisfying $\Omega_{A_2}^2 \tilde{\cap} \Omega_{A_1}^1 = \emptyset_A$. From $\Omega_{A_2}^2 \neq \emptyset_A$, we have an $e \in A_2$ and a $u \in U$ such that $\delta_{\Omega_{A_2}^2}^+(u) \neq 0$ or $\delta_{\Omega_{A_2}^2}^-(u) \neq 0$. Choose that $\delta_{\Omega_{A_2}^2}^+(u) \neq 0$. Also, we know that $\delta_{\Omega_{A_1}^1}^+(u) \neq 0$ for these $e \in E$ and $u \in U$. As a result, we obtain $\min\{\delta_{\Omega_{A_2}^2}^+(u), \delta_{\Omega_{A_1}^1}^+(u)\} \neq 0$, which is a contradiction.

Theorem 2.24. [6] Let F be an ultra BFS-filter on U , and let $Z \subseteq U$. Suppose there exists $\Omega_{A_Z}^* \in F$ such that for every for every $e \in E$ and $u \in U - Z$, $\delta_{\Omega_{A_Z}^*}^+(u) = 0$ and $\delta_{\Omega_{A_Z}^*}^-(u) = 0$. For each $\Omega_A \in F$, define $\Omega_{A_Z} = \Omega_A \tilde{\cap} Y^Z$. Then the family

$$F_A = \{\Omega_{A_Z} \mid \Omega_A \in F\}$$

is an ultra BFS-filter on Z .

Proof. First, let us show that F_A is a BFS-filter on Z .

(bfst₁) Assume that $\emptyset_A \in F_A$. Then, for some $\Omega_A \in F$, we have $\Omega_A \tilde{\cap} Y^Z = \emptyset_A$. This leads to a contradiction because $\Omega_A \tilde{\cap} \Omega_{A_Z}^* = \emptyset_A \in F$.

(bfst₂) Let $\Omega_{A_Z}, \Gamma_{B_Z} \in F_A$. In this instance, $\Omega_A, \Gamma_B \in F$, and thus $\Omega_A \tilde{\cap} \Gamma_B \in F$. Therefore, since $(\Omega_A \tilde{\cap} \Gamma_B)_Z = \Omega_{A_Z} \tilde{\cap} \Gamma_{B_Z}$, we have $\Omega_{A_Z} \tilde{\cap} \Gamma_{B_Z} \in F_A$.

(bfst₃) Let $\Omega_{A_Z} \in F_A$, and take $\Gamma_B \in (BF^Z)^E$ such that $\Omega_{A_Z} \subseteq \Gamma_B$. Define a BFS-set $\Lambda_C \in (BF^U)^E$ that contains Ω_A , where for every $e \in E$ and $u \in U$:

$$\delta_{\Lambda(e)}^+(u) = \begin{cases} \delta_{\Gamma(e)}^+(u), & u \in Z \\ 1, & u \notin Z \end{cases}$$

$$\delta_{\Lambda(e)}^-(u) = \begin{cases} \delta_{\Gamma(e)}^-(u), & u \in Z \\ -1, & u \notin Z \end{cases}$$

In this case, $\Lambda_C \in F$, and thus $\Gamma_B = \Lambda_{C_Z} \in F_A$.

Now, let us show that F_A is an ultra BFS-filter on Z . For every $\Omega_{A_Z} \in F_A$, there exists $\Gamma_B \in (BF^Z)^E$ such that $\Omega_{A_Z} \tilde{\cap} \Gamma_B \neq \emptyset_A$. Define a BFS-set $\Lambda_C \in (BF^U)^E$, where for every $e \in E$ and $u \in U$:

$$\delta_{\Lambda(e)}^+(u) = \begin{cases} \delta_{\Gamma(e)}^+(u), & u \in Z \\ 1, & u \notin Z \end{cases}$$

$$\delta_{\Lambda(e)}^-(u) = \begin{cases} \delta_{\Gamma(e)}^-(u), & u \in Z \\ -1, & u \notin Z \end{cases}$$

For every $\Omega_A \in F$, we have $\Omega_A \tilde{\cap} \Lambda_C \neq \emptyset_A$, and by Theorem 2.25, $\Lambda_C \in F$. Thus, $\Gamma_B = \Lambda_{C_Z} \in F_A$, and by Theorem 2.25, the desired result follows.

Definition 2.25 [24]. A binary relation $\rho \subseteq (BF^U)^E \times (BF^U)^E$ is a BFS-proximity on U_E if ρ satisfies the following axioms:

(bfsp₁) $\emptyset_A \bar{\rho} \Omega_A$.

(bfsp₂) If $\Omega_A \tilde{\cap} \Gamma_B \neq \emptyset_A$, then $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B$.

(bfsp₃) If $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B$, then $\Gamma_B \rho \Omega_A$.

(bfsp₄) $\Omega_A \rho (\Gamma_B \tilde{\cup} \Lambda_C)$ if and only if $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B$ or $\Omega_A \rho \Lambda_C$.

(bfsp₅) If $\Omega_A \bar{\rho} \Gamma_B$, then there exists a $\Lambda_C \in (BF^U)^E$ such that $\Omega_A \bar{\rho} \Lambda_C$ and $\Gamma_B \bar{\rho} (U_E - \Lambda_C)$.

The triplet (U, ρ, E) is called a BFS-proximity space.

Theorem 2.26. [24] Let $C : (BF^U)^E \rightarrow (BF^U)^E$ be an operator fulfilling the following conditions:

(bfo₁) $\Omega_A \cong C(\Omega_A)$.

(bfo₂) $C(C(\Omega_A)) = C(\Omega_A)$.

(bfo₃) $C(\Omega_A \tilde{\cup} \Gamma_B) = C(\Omega_A) \tilde{\cup} C(\Gamma_B)$.

(bfo₄) $\emptyset_A = C(\emptyset_A)$.

Then, we obtain a BFS-topology as below:

$$\tau = \{\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E : C((\Omega_A)^c) = (\Omega_A)^c\}.$$

Also, considering this BFS-topology, we establish that $\overline{\Omega_A} = C(\Omega_A)$ for every $\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E$. We refer to the operator C as the BFS-closure operator.

Lemma 2.27. [24] Consider a BFS-proximity space (U, ρ, E) .

Then, the following conditions are fulfilled:

- (i) If $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B$ and $\Delta_D \cong \Omega_A, \Lambda_C \cong \Gamma_B$, then $\Delta_D \rho \Lambda_C$.
- (ii) $\Omega_A \rho \Omega_A$ for each $\Omega_A \neq \emptyset_A$.
- (iii) $\Omega_A \rho U_E$ if and only if $\Omega_A \neq \emptyset_A$.

Theorem 2.28.[24] Let (U, ρ, E) be a BFS-proximity space.

Then, the mapping $\Omega_A \rightarrow \overline{\Omega_A}$ has the properties $(bfo_1) - (bfo_4)$. So, the family

$$\tau(\rho) = \{\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E : \overline{(\Omega_A)^c} = (\Omega_A)^c\}$$

is a BFS-topology on U_E .

3.BFS-Clusters

Definition 3.1. Let (U, ρ, E) be a BFS-proximity space and let $\sigma \subset (BF^U)^E$. Then σ is called a BFS-cluster on U if the following conditions are satisfied:

- (C1) If $\Omega_A, \Gamma_B \in \sigma$, then $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B$.
- (C2) For every $\Gamma_B \in \sigma$, if $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B$, then $\Omega_A \in \sigma$.
- (C3) If $\Omega_A \tilde{\cap} \Gamma_B \in \sigma$, then $\Omega_A \in \sigma$ or $\Gamma_B \in \sigma$.

Lemma 3.2. Let (U, ρ, E) be a BFS-proximity space. Then:

- (1) If there exist BFS-clusters σ_1 and σ_2 on U such that $\sigma_1 \subset \sigma_2$, then $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2$.
- (2) Let σ be a BFS-cluster. The following statements hold:
 - (i) If $\Omega_A \in \sigma$ and $\Omega_A \cong \Lambda_C$, then $\Lambda_C \in \sigma$.
 - (ii) $\emptyset_A \notin \sigma$ and $U_E \in \sigma$.
 - (iii) $\Omega_A \in \sigma$ if and only if $\overline{\Omega_A} \in \sigma$.

Proof (1) Let $\Omega_A \in \sigma_2$. Then, by condition (C1), for every $\Gamma_B \in \sigma_2$, we have $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B$. Since $\sigma_1 \subset \sigma_2$, it follows that $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B$ holds for every $\Gamma_B \in \sigma_1$. Thus, by condition (C2), $\Omega_A \in \sigma_1$.

(2) (i) Since $\Omega_A \in \sigma$, condition (C1) implies that for every $\Gamma_B \in \sigma$, $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B$ holds. Therefore, for every $\Gamma_B \in \sigma$, $\Lambda_C \rho \Gamma_B$, and hence $\Lambda_C \in \sigma$.

(ii) This follows directly from conditions (C1) and (C2).

(iii) Consider $\Omega_A \in \sigma$, we have noticed that $\Omega_A \cong \overline{\Omega_A}$. In this case, $\overline{\Omega_A} \in \sigma$ according to Lemma 3.2 2(i). Conversely, let $\overline{\Omega_A} \in \sigma$. Since $\Omega_A \rho \overline{\Omega_A}$, we obtain $\Omega_A \in \sigma$ by (C2).

Theorem 3.3 Let (U, ρ, E) be a BFS-proximity space, and let $\sigma \subset (BF^U)^E$ satisfy the following conditions:

- (i) $\emptyset_A \notin \sigma$,
- (ii) $\Omega_A \in \sigma \Leftrightarrow \overline{\Omega_A} \in \sigma$,
- (iii) $\Omega_A \tilde{\cup} \Gamma_B \in \sigma \Leftrightarrow \Omega_A \in \sigma$ or $\Gamma_B \in \sigma$.

Let $\Omega_{A_0}^0 \in \sigma$. Then there exists an ultra BFS-filter F on X

such that $\Omega_{A_0}^0 \in F \subset \sigma$.

Proof. Let Π denote the set of all subsets $\omega \subset (BF^U)^E$ satisfying the following two properties:

- (1) $\Omega_{A_0}^0 \in \omega$.
- (2) If $\Omega_{A_1}^1, \dots, \Omega_{A_n}^n \in \omega$, then $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \tilde{\cap} \dots \tilde{\cap} \Omega_{A_n}^n \in \sigma$.

By Zorn's Lemma, Π has a maximal element ω_0 . It is easily seen that $\Omega_{A_0}^0 \in \omega_0 \subset \sigma$. Now we show that ω_0 is a BFS-filter on U .

(S1) The condition is evident.

(S2) Let $\Omega_{A_1}^1, \Omega_{A_2}^2 \in \omega_0$. Then $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \tilde{\cap} \Omega_{A_2}^2 \in \sigma$. Since $\omega_0 \cup \{\Omega_{A_1}^1 \tilde{\cap} \Omega_{A_2}^2\} \in \Pi$, and by the maximality of ω_0 , we have $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \tilde{\cap} \Omega_{A_2}^2 \in \omega_0$.

(S3) Let $\Omega_A \in \omega_0$ and $\Omega_A \subseteq \Gamma_B$. Then $\Gamma_B = (\Gamma_B \tilde{\cup} \Omega_A) \in \sigma$. Thus, $\omega_0 \cup \{\Gamma_B\} \in \Pi$ implies $\Gamma_B \in \omega_0$.

Hence, ω_0 is a BFS-filter on U . By Theorem 5.3.2, there exists a BFS-ultrafilter F on U such that $\omega_0 \subset F$. If it can be shown that $F \subset \sigma$, the proof will be complete. Assume for contradiction that there exists a BFS-set $\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E$ such that $\Omega_A \in F$ but $\Omega_A \notin \sigma$. Then, by (ii), $\overline{\Omega_A} \notin \sigma$. Furthermore, $\overline{\Omega_A} \in F$ and $\overline{\Omega_A} \tilde{\cap} (U_E - \overline{\Omega_A}) = \emptyset_A$, so by Theorem 5.3.4 (i), $(U_E - \overline{\Omega_A}) \notin F$, and thus $(U_E - \overline{\Omega_A}) \notin \omega_0$. Now,

suppose that for every $\Lambda_C \in \omega_0$, $(U_E - \overline{\Omega_A}) \tilde{\cap} \Lambda_C \in \sigma$. Since ω_0 is a BFS-filter, if $\Lambda_{C_1}^1, \dots, \Lambda_{C_n}^n \in \omega_0$, then $\Lambda_{C_1}^1 \tilde{\cap} \dots \tilde{\cap} \Lambda_{C_n}^n \in \omega_0$. Therefore, $(U_E - \overline{\Omega_A}) \tilde{\cap} \Lambda_{C_1}^1 \tilde{\cap} \dots \tilde{\cap} \Lambda_{C_n}^n \in \sigma$. Thus, $\omega_0 \cup \{U_E - \overline{\Omega_A}\} \in \Pi$, which leads to a contradiction since $(U_E - \overline{\Omega_A}) \notin \omega_0$.

Hence, there exists an $\Lambda_C \in \omega_0$ such that $(U_E - \overline{\Omega_A}) \tilde{\cap} \Lambda_C \notin \sigma$. Moreover, since $\overline{\Omega_A} \notin \sigma$ and $(\overline{\Omega_A} \tilde{\cap} \Lambda_C) \cong \overline{\Omega_A}$, it follows that $(\overline{\Omega_A} \tilde{\cap} \Lambda_C) \notin \sigma$. By (iii), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_C = U_E \tilde{\cap} \Lambda_C &= (\overline{\Omega_A} \tilde{\cup} (U_E - \overline{\Omega_A})) \tilde{\cap} \Lambda_C \\ &= (\overline{\Omega_A} \tilde{\cap} \Lambda_C) \tilde{\cup} ((U_E - \overline{\Omega_A}) \tilde{\cap} \Lambda_C) \notin \sigma. \end{aligned}$$

This contradiction completes the proof.

Theorem 3.4. Let (U, ρ, E) be a BFS-proximity space, and let $\sigma \subset (BF^U)^E$. Then the following properties hold:

(i) σ is a BFS-cluster on U if and only if there exists an ultra BFS-filter F on U such that

$$\sigma = \{\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E \mid \text{for every } \Gamma_B \in F, \Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B\}.$$

(ii) If σ is a BFS-cluster and $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \in \sigma$, then there exists an ultra BFS-filter F on U such that $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \in F \subset \sigma$.

(iii) If σ is a BFS-cluster and there exists an ultra BFS-filter $F \subset \sigma$ on U , then

$$\sigma = \{\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E \mid \text{for every } \Gamma_B \in F, \Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B\}.$$

Proof (i) (\Leftarrow) Let us show that σ is a BFS-cluster on U .

(C1) Let $\Omega_A, \Gamma_B \in \sigma$. Suppose that $\Omega_A \bar{\rho} \Gamma_B$. By (bfp5), there exists an $\Lambda_C \in (BF^U)^E$ such that $\Omega_A \bar{\rho} \Lambda_C$ and $\Gamma_B \bar{\rho} (U_E - \Lambda_C)$.

Since $\Omega_A, \Gamma_B \in \sigma$, we have $\Lambda_C, (U_E - \Lambda_C) \notin F$. Thus, by Theorem 2.25, we reach a contradiction, implying $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B$.

(C2) Let $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B$ for any $\Gamma_B \in \sigma$. Clearly, $F \subseteq \sigma$. Indeed, if $\Lambda_C \in F$, then $\Lambda_C \tilde{\cap} \Lambda'_C \neq \emptyset_A$ for every $\Lambda'_C \in F$. Hence, $\Lambda_C \rho \Lambda'_C$ for every $\Lambda'_C \in F$, and we obtain $\Lambda_{C_1}^1 \in \sigma$. Since $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B$ exists for each $\Gamma_B \in \sigma$, it follows that $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B$ occurs for each $\Gamma_B \in F$. Therefore, we get $\Omega_A \in \sigma$.

(C3) Let $\Omega_A, \Gamma_B \notin \sigma$. Then there exist $\Lambda_{C_1}^1, \Lambda_{C_2}^2 \in F$ such that $\Omega_A \bar{\rho} \Lambda_{C_1}^1$ and $\Gamma_B \bar{\rho} \Lambda_{C_2}^2$. Define $\Lambda_C = \Lambda_{C_1}^1 \tilde{\cap} \Lambda_{C_2}^2$, so $\Lambda_C \in F$ and $(\Omega_A \tilde{\cup} \Gamma_B) \bar{\rho} \Lambda_C$. Hence, $(\Omega_A \tilde{\cup} \Gamma_B) \notin \sigma$.

(\Rightarrow) σ is a BFS-cluster and $\Omega_{A_0}^0 \in \sigma$. Then, by Theorem 3.3, there exists an ultra BFS-filter F on U such that $\Omega_{A_0}^0 \in F \subseteq \sigma$.

Let $\sigma_1 = \{\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E \mid \text{for every } \Gamma_B \in F, \Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B\}$. It is known that σ_1 is a BFS-cluster. Also, $\sigma \subseteq \sigma_1$. Indeed, if $\Lambda_C \in \sigma$, then $\Lambda_C \rho \Lambda'_C$ for every $\Lambda'_C \in \sigma$. Therefore, $\Lambda_C \rho \Lambda'_C$ for every $\Lambda'_C \in F$, implying $\Lambda_C \in \sigma_1$. Thus, by Lemma 3.2, we obtain $\sigma = \sigma_1$.

(ii) Follows easily from Theorem 3.3 Let σ be a BFS-cluster and $F \subseteq \sigma$ be an ultra BFS-filter on U . Let $\sigma_1 = \{\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E \mid \text{for every } \Gamma_B \in F, \Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B\}$. Then σ_1 is a BFS-cluster containing σ . Thus, by Lemma 3.2(i), we obtain $\sigma = \sigma_1$.

Corollary 3.5. Let (U, ρ, E) be a BFS-proximity space. Then, every ultra BFS-filter on U is contained in a unique BFS-cluster.

Proof. Let F be an ultra BFS-filter on U . Then, by Theorem 6.4.5, there exists a unique BFS-cluster $\sigma = \{\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E \mid \text{for every } \Gamma_B \in F, \Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B\}$ on U such that $F \subseteq \sigma$.

Theorem 3.6. Let (U, ρ, E) be a BFS-proximity space and let $\Omega_{A_0}^0, \Gamma_{B_0}^0 \in (BF^U)^E$. If $\Omega_{A_0}^0 \rho \Gamma_{B_0}^0$, then there exists a BFS-cluster σ on U such that $\Omega_{A_0}^0, \Gamma_{B_0}^0 \in \sigma$.

Proof. Let $\sigma_0 = \{\Omega_{A_0}^0 \in (BF^U)^E \mid \Omega_{A_0}^0 \rho \Gamma_{B_0}^0\}$. It is easily seen that the family σ_0 satisfies the following properties:

(i) $\Omega_{A_0}^0 \in \sigma_0$.

(ii) $\emptyset_A \notin \sigma_0$.

(iii) $\Omega_A \in \sigma_0 \Leftrightarrow \overline{\Omega_A} \in \sigma_0$.

(iv) $\Omega_A \tilde{\cup} \Gamma_B \in \sigma_0 \Leftrightarrow \Omega_A \in \sigma_0$ or $\Gamma_B \in \sigma_0$.

By Theorem 6.4.4, there exists an ultra BFS-filter F on U such that $\Omega_{A_0}^0 \in F \subseteq \sigma_0$. Let $\sigma = \{\Omega_A \in$

$(BF^U)^E \mid \text{for every } \Gamma_B \in F, \Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B\}$. By Theorem 6.4.5(i), σ is a BFS-cluster. On the other hand, $\Omega_{A_0}^0, \Gamma_{B_0}^0 \in \sigma$. In fact, if $\Lambda_C \in F$, then $\Lambda_C \in \sigma_0$ and hence we obtain $\Lambda_C \rho \Gamma_{B_0}^0$.

Therefore, since $\Lambda_C \rho \Gamma_{B_0}^0$ for all $\Lambda_C \in F$, it follows that $\Gamma_{B_0}^0 \in \sigma$. Moreover, since $F \subseteq \sigma$, we have $\Omega_{A_0}^0 \in \sigma$.

Theorem 3.7. Let (U, ρ_1, E) and (V, ρ_2, D) be two BFS-proximity spaces, and let $f : (U, \rho_1, E) \rightarrow (V, \rho_2, D)$ be a BFS-proximity mapping. If σ_1 is a BFS-cluster on U , then

$$\sigma_2 = \{\Lambda_C \in (BF^V)^D \mid \text{for all } \Gamma_B \in \sigma_1, \Lambda_C \rho_2 f(\Gamma_B)\}$$

is a BFS-cluster on V containing the family $f(\sigma_1)$.

Proof. According to Theorem 3.4(i), there exists an F an ultra BFS-filter on U such that

$$\sigma_1 = \{\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E \mid \text{for each } \Gamma_B \in F, \Omega_A \rho_1 \Gamma_B\}.$$

From Theorem 2.21, $B^* = \{f(\Omega_A) \mid \Omega_A \in F\}$ is a base for an ultra BFS-filter F^* on V . Thus, Theorem 3.4(i) implies that

$$\sigma_0 = \{\Lambda_C \in (BF^V)^D \mid \text{for each } \Gamma_B \in F^*, \Lambda_C \rho_2 \Gamma_B\}$$

is a BFS-cluster on V . First, let us show that $f(\sigma_1) \subseteq \sigma_0$. If $\Lambda_C \in f(\sigma_1)$, then there exists $\Omega_A \in \sigma_1$ such that $\Lambda_C = f(\Omega_A)$.

In this case, $\Omega_A \rho_1 \Gamma_B$ for each $\Gamma_B \in F$. Since f is a BFS-proximity mapping, $\Lambda_C \rho_2 f(\Gamma_B)$ holds for each $f(\Gamma_B) \in B^*$.

Thus, for every $\Omega'_A \in F^*$, we have $\Lambda_C \rho_2 \Omega'_A$. Therefore, $\Lambda_C \in \sigma_0$.

Now, to complete the proof, it remains to show that $\sigma_2 = \sigma_0$.

Let $\Lambda_C \in \sigma_2$. Since $F \subseteq \sigma_1$, we have $\Lambda_C \rho_2 f(\Gamma_B)$ for each $\Gamma_B \in F$. Therefore, $\Lambda_C \in \sigma_0$. Thus, by Lemma 3.2(1) we obtain $\sigma_2 = \sigma_0$.

Definition 3.8. Let (U, ρ, E) be a BFS-proximity space and $A \subseteq U$. Let ρ_A be the BFS-proximity induced by ρ , and let $f : (A, \rho_A, E) \rightarrow (U, \rho, E)$ be a BFS-mappings. If $u : A \rightarrow U$ and $g : E \rightarrow E$ are inclusion mapping, then the mapping $f : (A, \rho_A, E) \rightarrow (U, \rho, E)$ is called a BFS-inclusion mapping.

Theorem 3.9. Let (U, ρ, E) be a BFS-proximity space and $Z \subseteq U$. If σ_1 is a BFS-cluster on Z , then

$$\sigma_2 = \{\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E \mid \text{for every } \Gamma_B \in \sigma_1, \Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B\}$$

is a BFS-cluster on U .

Proof. Let $(Z, \rho_Z, E) \rightarrow (U, \rho, E)$ be a BFS-inclusion mapping. Since $f(\Omega_A) = \Omega_A$ for every $\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E$, this mapping is a BFS-proximity mapping. Therefore, by Theorem 6.4.8, the desired result is easily obtained.

Theorem 3.10. Let (U, ρ, E) be a BFS-proximity space, σ be a BFS-cluster on U , and let $Z \subseteq U$. Suppose that there exists an $\Omega_{A_Z}^* \in \sigma$ such that for every $e \in E$ and $u \in U - Z$,

$\delta_{\Omega_Z^*(e)}^+(u) = 0$ and $\delta_{\Omega_Z^*(e)}^-(u) = 0$. Then,

$$\sigma_1 = \{\Omega_A \in \sigma \mid \text{for every } e \in E \text{ and every } u \in U - Z, \delta_{\Omega_Z^*(e)}^+(u) = 0 \text{ and } \delta_{\Omega_Y^*(e)}^-(u) = 0\}$$

is a BFS-cluster on Z .

Proof. Let σ be a BFS-cluster on U , and let $\Omega_{A_Z}^* \in \sigma$. By Theorem 3.6, there exists an ultra BFS-filter F on U such that $\sigma = \{\Omega_A \in (BF^U)^E \mid \text{for every } \Gamma_B \in F, \Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B\}$, where $\Omega_{A_Z}^*$ is contained in the BFS-set on U .

For each $\Omega_A \in F$, let $\Omega_{A_Z} = \Omega_A \tilde{\cap} Y^Z$, and define $F_Z = \{\Omega_{A_Z} \mid \Omega_A \in F\}$. By Theorem 2.26, the family F_Z is a BFS-filter on A . Hence,

$$\sigma_0 = \{\Omega_A \in (BF^Z)^E \mid \text{for every } \Gamma_{B_Z} \in F_Z, \Omega_A \rho_Z \Gamma_{B_Z}\}$$

is a BFS-cluster on A . If we can show that $\sigma_0 = \sigma_1$, the proof is complete.

Let $\Omega_A \in \sigma_0$. Then for every $\Gamma_B \in F, \Omega_A \rho_Z \Gamma_{B_Z}$, and therefore $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_{B_Z}$. Since $\Gamma_{B_Z} \subseteq \Gamma_B$, it follows that $\Omega_A \rho \Gamma_B$ for every $\Gamma_B \in F$, which implies that $\Omega_A \in \sigma$. As $\Omega_A \in (BF^Z)^E$, we conclude that $\Omega_A \in \sigma_1$.

Now, let $\Omega_A \in \sigma_1$. Take a BFS-set $\Gamma_{B_Z} \in F_Z$. Then $\Omega_{A_1}^1 = (\Gamma_B \tilde{\cap} \Omega_{A_Z}^*) \in F$, and hence $\Omega_A \rho \Omega_{A_1}^1$. Since $\Omega_{A_1}^1, \Omega_A \in (BF^Z)^E$, by the definition of ρ_Z , we obtain $\Omega_A \rho_Z \Omega_{A_1}^1$.

Furthermore, since $\Omega_{A_1}^1 \subseteq \Gamma_{B_Z}$, it follows that $\Omega_A \rho_Z \Gamma_{B_Z}$.

Therefore, for every $\Gamma_{B_Z} \in F_Z, \Omega_A \rho_Z \Gamma_{B_Z}$, and thus $\Omega_A \in \sigma_0$.

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